

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH THE COMPONENT OF TEMPORALITY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

Phrases expressing the concept of time in the Uzbek language and the division of these concepts into semantic groups.

In the Uzbek language phraseological expressions forming concept “time” are the following set expressions containing words *kun, ertalab, tong, kecha: kun bo’yi* – all day long, *kundan kunga* – day by day, *butun kun* – the whole day, *ertalabdan kechgacha* – from morning till night, *tong-azondan, kallayi saharlab* – at an unearthly hour, *tunu-kun* – day and night, *kuppa-kunduz kuni* – in broad daylight. Most of set expressions reflecting the concept time are in their syntactic properties idiomatic units with qualitative-adverbial characteristics as they tell the time when the action is performed. Such set phrases play an important role in the formation of understanding the spatial-temporal organization of reality and uncover the ideas about the category of time in linguistic cognition of language bearers. This refers to such phraseological units in the English as: the golden age, the clock round, all day long, only a short while ago, day-to-day, day and night, in any moment, from dawn to dusk, and etc. As we see, these expressions contain such nouns in their structure as morning, day, night, dawn, dusk, and prepositions from, till, in, and etc.

Of course the above mentioned expressions make up only a small part of all set expressions expressing time. Phraseological units forming this concept can be divided into the following semantic groups:

1. The first group includes qualitative-adverbial idioms expressing the time of the day when the action happens. These phraseological units tell that the action happens in the morning, afternoon, or evening. The components of such idiomatic phrases are closely connected with their semantics. They are usually formed with such nouns as evening, day, morning, dawn.

2. The second group of set expressions is formed with idioms expressing a very short period of time – blink, instant, moment, second, minute, flash: for instant, for a second, in a twinkling of an eye, on the stroke, on the dot, in a minute, half a moment, in a flash. The semantics of a word in these expressions changes into a general meaning expressing a very short period of time. There are similar set expressions in Uzbek that also express short moment: *bir lahzada, bir pasda, dam o’tmay, bir onda* – on the stroke, in a minute, bir

zumda, “hash-pash” deguncha, “ha-hu” deguncha – in a flash, ko’z ochib yumguncha – in a twinkling of an eye.

3. The third group of set expressions unite the units expressing indefinitely long period of time. Structurally, they can be grouped into the following classes: “noun + noun with preposition” based on repetition: day by day (kundan-kunga), from day to day, day and night (tunu-kun); set expressions formed of “pronoun + noun”- all the day, all the time (har on) «adjective+noun» yil bo’yi, yil o’n ikki oy, and etc.

4. The fourth group of idioms include set expressions characterizing the starting point of the action: since the beginning of time (qadimdan, azaldan, ko’pdan beri, ro’si azal), then a days (o’sha paytda, o’sha davrda, o’sha zamonda, o’sha kezda), for the time being (vaqti-soati kelguncha). Their structure contain such noun components that name indefinite periods of time – «time», «days». Usually idioms expressing the beginning period of the action are used after a certain flow of events that bring about the beginning of a new period of life.

5. The fifth semantic group includes set expressions denoting the beginning and end of human life: on the go, (kun (i)bitdi, kun(i) tugadi), in the vale of years, in the afternoon of life (qariganda, qarigan chog’da). There are also idioms expressing indefinite time close in the meaning to never, when two Sundays come in one week, in a pigs eye, when cows come home. Uzbek language is also rich in such idioms that express the notion of never. For example: hapshanba kuni, tuyaning dumi yerga tekkanda, hukiz tuqqanda, and etc. Knowing the above mentioned semantic groups is very helpful in translating fiction from English into Uzbek and vice versa. Below we shall give some examples of translating phraseological units from English into Uzbek on the example of the translation made by

Muhabbat Ismailova of the book by Jane Austin “Pride and Prejudice”. -in a moment “A lady's imagination is very rapid; it jumps from admiration to love, from love to matrimony, in a moment.” “Ayollarning tasavvuri qanchalik tez-a!” In a moment they were all out of the chaise, rejoicing at the sight of each other. Mrs. Collins welcomed her friend with the liveliest pleasure, and Elizabeth was more and more satisfied with coming when she found herself so affectionately received. Kelganlar o’sha zahoti karetdan tushib uy egalari bilan ko’rishga ketishdi. -one day After a few minutes' reflection, however, she continued, «I do remember his boasting one day, at Netherfield, of the implacability of his resentments, of his having an unforgiving temper...” Bir oz jimlikdan so’ng, Elizabeth gapida davom etdi: “Hozir bir kuni Nezerfildda u o’zining haddan tashqari ginachi ekanligini aytgani esimga tushdi. Qanday murakkab tabiatli kishi! Mr. Bennet treated the matter differently. «So, Lizzy,» said he one day, «your sister is crossed in love, I find. I congratulate her.” Mister Bennetning fikri esa bu borada butunlay boshqacha edi: “Shunday qilib, Lizzi, anglashimcha, opangning yuragi bir oz yaralandi, – dedi u bir kuni.- Uni meni nomimdan tabriklab qo’y. ” -from this day «An unhappy alternative is before you, Elizabeth. From this day you must be a stranger to one of your parents. Your mother will never see you again if you do not marry Mr. Collins, and I will never see you again if you do.» “Demak, qizim, sening sharoiting hozir juda og’ir. Shu daqiqadan boshlab sen yoki mendan, yoki onangdan ayrilasan. Agar sen Kollinzga turmushga chiqmaydigan bo’lsang, onang sendan kechadi, agar unga turmushga chiqadigan bo’lsang, men seni ko’rishni istamayman.” -the other day «As I did the other day,» said Elizabeth with a conscious smile: «very true, it will be wise in me to refrain from that. But do not imagine that he is always here

so often. It is on your account that he has been so frequently invited this week. “Kecha qilganimni atyapsizmi? – qizarib so’radi Eliza. – Ha siz haqsiz. Men noto’g’ri ish qildim. Lekin siz u doimo biznikida ekan deb o’ylamang. Bu hafta uni sizlar shu yerda ekanligingiz uchungina taklif qildik.” -all day long –«Oh! Yes—the handsomest young lady that ever was seen; and so accomplished!— She plays and sings all day long. In the next room is a new instrument just come down for her — a present from my master; she comes here to-morrow with him.» “Shubhasiz! – xitob qildi missis Reynolds. – U dunyodagi eng go’zallardan qolishmaydi. Yana qanday tarbiyasi! Ertadan kechgacha musiqa bilan shug’ullanadi. Yonimizdagi xonada yaqindagina olib kelishgan musiqa asbobini ko’rasizlar – xo’jayinimizning miss Darsiga sovg’asi. Biz ertaga u ham akasi bilan kelishini kutaymiz.”. As we see from the above brought examples, idiomatic expressions expressing the concept “time” in the English are translated into Uzbek either with their equivalent set expressions in the target

language, or sometimes by free word combinations.

Comparative analysis of the semantic structure of the word “time” – “vaqt” in three different system languages allows revealing rich connotation (perhaps, it is motivated by how invaluable the concept of time is for humanity), to reveal similar variants of phraseological units like: for the time there is a time for all things – everything has its time – har bir narsaning o’z vaqti soati bor; one time or another – sooner or later – ertami kechmi; Vaqt chog’ (Chog’) – in a cheerful mood echoes the meaning of idioms in English have a fine time – meaning: have a good time, have fun. A comparative analysis of the semantic structure of the connotative meanings of the word «time» in Uzbek languages allows us to draw the following conclusions. Despite the fact that each of these languages has clichéd units peculiar only to them with the component “time”, one can find in Uzbek languages equivalent phraseological units and similar in semantics.

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